

Exploring biographies: finding new group members based on significant terms

User motivation

The development of the method is motivated by the need of historians to detect new group members, when working with social or religious (or otherwise defined) groups.

Defining the actors, which are crucial for developing particular phenomena, understanding the interconnections between them and their impact is a basal part of the work as a humanist. However, once covered the main group of actors, it can be challenging going above the known circle of biographies and find other possible members, which are not labeled as a group member, but still meet the criteria. The paper describes an exploratory method of finding new group members.

For the use case below, founding new group members (above the given 32-biography set) helped to see interconnections with other historically relevant personalities, such as German and Russian nobles.

Developer motivation

With respect to the quantitative methods applied, the primary purpose of this contribution is the presentation of significant terms as an appropriate interaction medium between scholars and algorithms that either extract or utilize such wordlists. We chose to focus on manually selected sets of biographies:

1. methods can be applied to extract terms that are quantitatively significant to these biographies,
2. these extracted wordlists qualify as immediately verifiable means for manual refinement of either the set of selective biographies or the wordlists themselves and
3. as such allow an iterative combination of qualitative and quantitative methods.

The transparency and control mechanisms of the approach allow an iterative process of finding significant terms and candidate biographies. As such, the overall concept might find acceptance of scholarly users, since instead of having to customize unfamiliar parameters as e.g. the desired amount of clusters or topics, scholars are exposed to the intuitive parameter of the wordlists themselves.

Research objectives

The ultimate aim of the project is to present a tool, which identifies biographical claims within biographical text, cluster biographies into groups, and be able to show geographical dynamics. Currently, CosmoTool can extract biographical information and form a timeline of a biography, considering important life stations.

Current tasks of the project are to determine how scholarly users can interact with the tool to define groups (1) and to receive candidate persons that qualify as group members (2). With respect to the motivation above, humanists should be able to define groups based on delimiting features of these groups, and receive persons, which show the features of a given group.

In this paper, the tool and the method of finding new group members is presented.

Data

Analyses are currently based on biographies of historical personalities from Wikipedia and Wikidata. The set of Wikipedia biographies has been purposely chosen due to its dimensions and interlinked nature, which facilitates the application and evaluation of quantitative methods. Wikipedia, as a biggest repository of historical personalities, offers a great field for searching new members. (The produced results however should be verified by the domain experts, and possibly compared with other encyclopedia manually.)

Choosing the significant biographies and compiling training material

32 biographies in German language were chosen by (*excluded from the abstract*) as training material for the algorithm. The group of historical actors (see table 1 in appendix) was chosen due to the criteria of connection (direct or indirect) to the German-speaking persons in St. Petersburg of the 18th century and their involvement in cultural and/or political life of the

given period. This connection was not always signified in the Wikipedia biography (either through text or Wikidata), so only through the expertise in the area a connection could have been established. The other important criteria was belonging of the German-speaking actors to the Lutheran or Reformed denominations.

Methodology

For the experiment, a corpus of around 430k biographies of the German Wikipedia were analyzed and indexed. Thereby, only the abstract and any main section with a biographically relevant heading were processed. All biographical texts were converted to lowercase, function words were removed and tokens were normalized and stemmed. The application of further analyses e.g. to detect named entities and temporal statements is expected to improve experiment as such entities could be treated accordingly.

Results

The table 2 (see appendix) shows a subset of 20 significant terms for each group. Next to the term you find the count of hits of the respective term in the set of 32 biographies (“Treffer Subset”) followed by the count of hits in the remainder of the ~430k biographical entries in the corpus (“Treffer Superset”).

The screenshot displays the CosmoTool interface for a specific group. The main heading is "The pietistic Network in St. Petersburg (late 17th -18th cent)" with 32 members. The "Signifikante Terme" section contains a table with the following data:

Term	Score	Treffer Subset	Treffer Superset
Mureentrost	1	3	3
Zwangs	0.376	3	8
kantschalkausgesprochen	0.3333	3	9
stiller	0.2308	3	13
bering	0.1301	4	41
osow	0.1034	3	29
kantschaika	0.1008	4	53
abrennung	0.075	3	40

Below the table, the "Personen" section shows a list of members. Two members are visible:

- Stepan Petrowitsch Krascheninnikow, Stepan Krascheninnikow (geboren 30.10.1711, gestorben 24.02.1755)
- Andreas Schlüter (gestorben 31.12.1713)

Based on the subset of significant terms a list of new 14 members is established. CosmoTool shows the significant terms placed in the biographies.

The pietistic Network in St. Petersburg (late 17th -18th cent)

32 Mitglieder

Personengruppen

Hinzufügen

- Muslimen
- Katholiken
- Protestanten
- The pietistic Network in St. Petersburg (late 17th -18th cent)

Suche

- Personensuche
- Wörterbuch

Mein Cosmotool

- Administration
- Sammlungen
- Datenreife
- Anpassungen
- Benutzersachen

cosmotool - Personengruppen - Gruppe: The pietistic Network in St. Petersburg (late 17th -18th cent)

Signifikante Terme

Terminwörter Tabelle

Term	Score Φ	Treffersubset	Treffersuperset	
blumenrost	1	3	3	0
berings	0.375	3	8	0
kamtschatkaspedition	0.3333	3	9	0
abster	0.2308	3	13	0
beringy	0.1301	4	41	0
asow	0.1034	3	29	0
kamtschatka	0.1006	4	53	0
sibirien	0.075	3	40	0

Gesperrte Terme

Keine gesperrten Terme hinterlegt.

Manuelle Terme +

Keine manuellen Terme hinzugefügt.

Personen

Mitglieder Kandidaten

Angezeigt werden 14 von 14 Treffern

Abraham Petrowitsch Hannibal, Abram Petrovich Gannibal

geboren 31.12.1695

Text

- Abraham **Petrowitsch** Hannibal, (* um 1696 in Logon Ghewan in Estria oder Logone-Beni, Kammanrei/Deudloon) Gnammarkos Abraham Hannibal – Fawad hor
- **Petersburg** war Sohn eines lokalen afrikanischen Fürsten in „Logon“ und **russischer** Generalmajor und Gouverneur von Rival, 1759 Oberbefehlshaber (General-en-Chef)
- Hof sowie Palastkind **Peters** des Großen.
- Unter den Pagen von **Zar Peter** dem Großen befand sich eine Zeit lang ein junger dunkelhäutiger Mann namens Abraham (siehe Puschkins Novelle „Der Mohr“
- des **Zaren**“)
- Juli 1705 in Wilna als Peter **Petrowitsch** Petrow (Петр Петрович Петров, wörtlich übersetzt: Peter; Sohn des Peter; **Peters** Sohn) getauft worden, dann in
- den Dienst des **Zaren** getreten und habe ihn auf Anhieb durch seine Freundlichkeit und seine Intelligenz bezaubert.
- Der **Zar** schätzte den Ernst und die Ergebenheit dieses Gefolgsmannes.
- Nach **Zar Peters** Tod fiel Hannibal politischen Intrigen zum Opfer und wurde 1727 nach **Sibirien** in die Verbannung geschickt.
- Drei Jahre später konnte er wieder an den **russischen** Hof zurückkehren.
- **Petersburg**: Er habe unter acht **Zaren** bzw. Zarinnen und unter zwei osmanischen Sultanen (Mustafa II. und Ahmed III.) gedient.
- Abraham **Petrowitsch** Hannibal war zweimal verheiratet.

Pylyp Orlyk

geboren 10.11.1672; gestorben 25.05.1742

Text

- Seine Kosaken bildeten den Kern der Rebellion von Iwan Masepa, die jedoch in die katastrophale Niederlage in der Schlacht bei **Poltawa** am 8.
- Im darauffolgend ausbrechenden Krieg der osmanischen Türken mit Russland fiel Orlyk mit osmanischer und krimtatarischer Hilfe in die **russische** Ukraine ein.
- Dem von Russlands **Zar** Peter dem Großen bereits 1705 anstelle Masepas eingesetzten Hetman Iwan Skoropadsky konnte er zwar nicht vertreiben, die seinen
- Horden unermüdet geklagene "Übergangnahme" des **Zaren** auf dem Schlachtfeld am Pruth aber ermöglichte dem Osmanischen Reich 1711 einen vorteilhaften Frieden
- Die Russen mussten Lozogedl zahlen, den Hetman **Asow** zurückgeben, und zumindest die Saporoscher Kosaken unterstellten ihr Gebiet dem osmanischen Sultans.
- Jensen, Lund 1909: p. 170 (schwedisch)/ref Nach Karls Tod im Dezember 1718 wurde dessen Schwester Ulrika Eleonore Königin von Schweden und der Große **Nordische**
- aus, dass eine große Koalition zwischen den bestimmenden europäischen Mächten sowie der osmanischen Partei im Entstehen war, die sich vereint gegen den **Zaren**
- mazepahstroskad@jmsuoftllpage:178/mode:2up "Mazepa: festmaka bilder fran Ukraia och Karl XII's dagar" Åhröd Jersén, Lund 1909: p. 178 (schwedisch)/ref Um **russischen**
- Man bedurfte ihm, dass es besser sei, wenn er sich um einen Ausgleich mit dem **russischen Zaren** bemühen würde
- Schweden hatte sich im Laufe des Jahres 1721 entschieden, seine europäischen Großmachtsambitionen gegenüber dem **russischen Zaren** endgültig aufzugeben.
- Der Frieden von Nystad beendete im Spätsommer von 1721 den Großen **Nordischen** Krieg zwischen Schweden und Russland.
- **Petersburg**: nach einem Brief an den **russischen** Palatin und Metropolit von Rjasan, Stefan Javonik [1688-1722]refhttp://www.gro.com/dele-book/1895/0
- Seit 1735 tobte ein neuer **russisch-türkischer** Krieg, die Kosaken hatten erneut die Seiten gewechselt, und die Österreicher hatten sich mit den Russen gegen
- Österreich besiegen und auf dem Balkan zurückdrängen, doch im Frieden mit Russland musste das Osmanische Reich 1739 endgültig auf die Saporoscher Region und **Asow**

Interpretation

Utilizing the wordlists for the identification of further candidates proves as a suitable method for finding new candidates that are loosely connected to the original group. Through this method the new actors were found, which belonged to military nobility and to German speaking commune (Abraham Hannibal, Balthasar Freiherr von Campenhausen, Ludwig Nikolaus von Hallart). 2 members were not of German origin, but their line of work (a personal physician of the impress, a scientist and a navigator/explorer) let us assume a connection to German-speaking circle (Louis De l'Isle de la Croyère, Joseph Billings).

7 biographies of the total 14 however, do not qualify: they are either of the later century, or have no connection to the German-speaking community of the given time.

The described method allowed the user to search for new candidates, without defining search words first, but be led solely through the "textual logic" of the biographies. In this given experiment, the found words ("significant terms") were less intuitive for the user.

Future objectives

In order to make the interaction between algorithm and a user even more precise an opportunity of adding new words and deleting unsuitable ones in the significant terms list is implemented and should be tested.

Appendix is excluded from the extract due to word limit.